

An Inclusive ERA for Excellent Research

Science Europe's Reaction to the Commission Proposal for a Council Recommendation on a Pact for Research and Innovation

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Science Europe, bringing forward the perspective of the major national research performing and research funding organisations, supports the development of a Pact for Research and Innovation that includes R&I-related values and principles. It, therefore, welcomes the European Commission's (EC) adoption of the Council's Recommendations on a Pact for Research and Innovation and commends the efforts of the ERA Forum for Transition in developing the Pact.

The Pact for Research and Innovation needs to be based on common values and concrete commitments

The Pact needs to reflect the values that underpin the research ecosystem. In this context, Science Europe welcomes the inclusion of a common set of values and principles in the EC's proposals that it also shares, as well as the Pact's emphasis on research and scientific knowledge.

Member States should also provide adequate funding for R&I, which is key to achieving the European Research Area (ERA). Science Europe has long advocated for the reaffirmation of the investment target of 3% of EU GDP dedicated to research and development, as well as the new 1.25% EU GDP public effort target to be achieved by Member States by 2030. As a result, their inclusion in the EC's proposal is welcome, and it is essential that the Council Recommendations includes them as well.

A systematic inclusion of R&I stakeholders is crucial

The Pact must be implemented in a relevant way for the research activity in the ERA, meaningfully involving research communities and R&I stakeholders in the development and implementation of ERA policies. Science Europe looks forward to a more structured and systemic approach to stakeholder's involvement. Pan-European stakeholders represent the organisations and bodies that implement the ERA on the ground. Research funders, research performers, and universities play a fundamental role in advancing the ERA. Science Europe builds on the expertise and experience of its members to contribute to a strong and open ERA.

The European Research Area needs to be inclusive to be successful

The ERA, as a political vision for Europe, should consider that not all European countries are EU Member States, and that, together, we are able to actively and constructively contribute to a European research ecosystem that is globally competitive. Science Europe welcomes the emphasis on global outreach and cooperation with third countries and calls for the countries associated to the EU Framework Programmes, in particular the UK and Switzerland, to be included in ERA's development process.

About Science Europe

Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking research in Europe. It brings together the expertise of 38 of the largest and best-known research organisations in the world to jointly push the frontiers of how scientific research is produced and delivers benefits to society. It advocates science and the scientific community to help build the European Research Area (ERA) and shape the global scientific agenda.

Science Europe member organisations develop, manage, and implement national research policies, as well as a large variety of funding programmes, from bottom-up schemes to mission-oriented research. They collectively invest over €23.9 billion each year on research in 28 European countries. Science Europe members are also developing and adapting national policies on an on-going basis to create the best possible conditions for research.